

THE ROLE OF METAL SURFACE PROPERTIES ON ADHESION INTERACTION WITH POLYOLEFINS IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Laimonis Malers, Aldis Sirmacs
Riga Technical University
Azenes str. 14, LV 1048 Riga, Latvia

ABSTRACT

A large scale of differently prepared metal surfaces have been studied by scanning electronic microscopy. The presence of two groups of failure mode (i) near the interface and (ii) in the bulk of adhesive have been taken as a base in analysing of the role of metal surface state in adhesive bonding with polyethylene. The importance of specific adhesion in providing of high strength properties of adhesive joints has been stated.

Keywords: topography of metal surface, adhesive joint, failure mode, polyolefins, weak boundary layer.

1. INTRODUCTION

A number of works are devoted to clearing of mechanisms of adhesion¹⁻³, although complex theoretical baseground of adhesion isn't created. Therefore each couple of joining materials demands a certain amount of investigations.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Adhesive: high density polyethylene ($M_m=158.000$, $M_m/M_n=6,8$) and ethylene vinylacetate copolymer with content of vinylacetate 16% by weight are used.

Substrates: steel, aluminium and copper are used in form of foils, 100, 200 and 100 μm thickness respectively. Preparation of surface prior contacting has been done according to different former described methods^{1,4} recovered in table 1.

Sandwich type adhesive joints are prepared by direct compression of melt of adhesive between two sheets of metal in closed form under pressure 0,4 MPa in temperature 180 °C, 5 minutes.

Table 1. Surface preparation of metals and adhesion with PE.

Metal surface preparation	Peeling strength, kN/m
Steel	
1. Electrochemical degreasing in alkali solution	0
2. Etching in HCl	1,0
3. Etching in HNO ₃	0,97
4. Anodizing in H ₂ SO ₄	0,46
5. Etching in HCl and treating in chromic acid	1,50
6. Oxidation in damp N ₂ in 450 °C	3,4
Aluminium	
7. Degreasing in NaOH	0
8. Sulphuric acid anodizing	3,0
9. Phosphoric acid anodizing (PAA)	5,8
10. Anodizing in NaOH and NaCl	0,75
11. Phosphoric acid anodizing and treating in chromic acid	6,10
Copper	
12. Degreasing in alkali solution	0
13. Etching in HNO ₃ and H ₃ PO ₄	0
14. Oxidation in NaOH and Na ₂ S ₂ O ₈	1,6

3. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

3.1. Failure Mode of Adhesive Joints

Well known and widely proved is the fact that during mechanical delamination of adhesive joints failure never occurs clearly in the interface adhesive – substrate^{1,5,6}. Even in case of self-delamination traces of weak boundary layer residuing on metal are easily detectable by contact angle measurements. However practically important is dividing of adhesive joints in two groups. (i) Failure occurs apparently adhesively (figure 1.) without remarkable deformation of adhesive. Respectively only a thin layer of low molecular weight products remains on the metal surface.

(ii) Failure occurs clearly in the bulk of adhesive (figure 2.) and both sides represent a feature of polymer. Although deformation of polymer on the surface of adhesive and substrate is different it allows to consider that failure takes place in the layer with the highest gradient of physico-mechanical properties of adhesive. Thereby in the process of delamination a considerably thicker layer of adhesive than one in the first case takes part and greater values of peeling strength appear as a consequence.

Taking into account the fact that conditions of obtaining of adhesive joints are equal, dissimilarities of interfacial region in adhesives are subjected to different state of metal surface only.

Figure 1. Micrographs of steel (a) and PE (b) surfaces after delamination.
Steel surface etched in HNO_3 .

Figure 2. Micrographs of Al (a) and PE (b,c) surfaces after delamination.
Al surface prepared by PAA process.

3.2. Comparison of Metal Surface Properties

Collected experience clearly shows that both — cohesive and adhesive delamination of adhesive joints as well as reached strength of peeling can be high and low on different topography of metal surfaces. For instance, in comparison of figure 1. and 3. (the latter represents the surface of aluminium prepared by PAA process, respective delaminated adhesive joint in figure 2.).

The same absence of direct correlation is between the strength properties of adhesive joints and acidity of prepared metal surfaces. (Evaluation of the later was performed by pH measurements of water extracts, obtained from treating of determinate amount of metal in ultrasonic bath.). All tested surfaces indicated pH from 5,1 to 7,2 and there are no logical connection with relation to strength of

Figure 3. Initial state of Al after PAA process.

adhesive joints with two different adhesives PE and ethylene vinylacetate copolymer. Apparently it is due to the fact that in the process of the surface preparing simultaneously complex changes take place in its topography, energetics and physico-chemical properties. Each of them can play an important role in providing adhesiveness of substrate towards polyolefins.

Finally some complementar aspects of adhesive interaction that can be important in certain cases.

(i) It is estimated on model systems (powder with highly developed surfaces⁷) that low molecular weight products what appear on interface in process of crystallization can be partially removed by sorption of metal surface. Thereby the formation of the weak boundary layer becomes less expressed.

(ii) Structure of substrate surface can initiate nucleation of adhesive³ and as process of crystallization starts from the side of metal then formation of weak boundary layer can be prevented or moved back in the bulk. As a result properties of boundary layers become closer to the bulk ones. In that way one can conclude that both the rough and the smooth surfaces of metal are potentially able to form a strong bond with adhesive if specific adhesion takes place.

References

1. *Adhesion Aspects of Polymer Coatings*, Ed. by K.L.Mittal, Proceedings of Symposium, Plenum Press, New York, 1983, pp. 649.
2. Allen K.W., *A Review of Contemporary Views of Theories of Adhesion*, J. Adhesion, Vol. 21, No. 4, 1990, pp. 261 - 277.
3. Schonhorn H., *Adhesion and Adhesives: Interaction at Interfaces*, Proc. of Conf. Adhes. Cellul. and Wood - Based Compos, Plenum Press, New York, 1980, pp. 91 - 111.
4. Wegman R.F., *Surface Preparation Techniques for Adhesive Bonding*, Noyes Publications, New Jersey, U.S.A. 1989, pp. 150.
5. Bikerman J.J., *About Probability of Adhesive Failure*, Polymer Mechanics, No. 3, 1973, pp. 516 - 519.
6. Ozolins J.J., Kalnins M.M., Dzenis M.J., *Localization of Cohesive Failure of Adhesive Joints Polyolefin - Steel*, Mechanics of Composit Materials, No. 3, 1986, Riga, pp. 415 - 418.
7. Miranovic A.A., Malers L.J., Lukjancikova M.S., *Connection Between Surface Characteristics of Aluminium Oxide and Adhesion of Filled Polyethylene to Steel*, Modification of Polymer Materials, 1983, Riga, pp. 32 - 38.

SMART COMPOSITES AND MANUFACTURING
